

Suspected Rhetorical Dualities (An Original Study (Similarity And Metaphor Between Truth And Metaphor)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Rhetorical Dualities, Suspect, Simile And Metonymy, Truth And Metaphor</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6332918</p>	<p><i>Before we enter into the subject of rhetoric among the rhetorical arts, we must know what is the difference between statement, truth, disclosure and other conventions of truth?</i></p> <p><i>The answer to this question is found by Al-Sakaki when he declared: "Metaphor is more eloquent than truth, metaphor is stronger than declaring simile, and metaphor is more effective than declaring dhikr" (Al-Sakaki: 412).</i></p> <p><i>Al-Sakaki contrasted his saying between metaphor, reality and metaphor, and the statement by simile, metaphor, and disclosure. Al-Qazwini followed Al-Sakaki, saying: "The rhetoricians applied that metaphor is more eloquent than truth, and that metaphor is more eloquent than declaring by analogy, and that representation by metaphor is more eloquent than representation, not by metaphor, and metaphor is more eloquent than disclosure by remembrance" (Al-Qazwini: 1/310-311).). All of this means, for them, that speech is either true or metaphorical, metaphor is either a metaphor or a simile, and the truth is either a metaphor or a statement.</i></p>

Introduction

First: The metaphor between truth and metaphor

Al-Halabi conveyed to us the difference between the rhetoricians in the metaphor, "Some of them said that it is from the section of truth, and some of them said that it is from the section of metaphor, and some of them said that it is a word that is pulled by the two sides of truth and metaphor, and some of them did not judge it by truth or metaphor" (Al-Halabi: 101).

Al-Jurjani decided that representation and simile only follow metaphor (Al-Jurjani: Asrar al-Balaghah: 202), meaning that they are from the door of metaphor and not metonymy as well. The first includes metonymy, metaphor, and representation that is on the limit of metaphor, i.e.: "Everything in the sentence is metaphor, breadth, and deviation from the apparent meaning" (Al-Jurjani: Al-Dala'il: 429-430), and here he makes the metaphor of the metaphor.

On the other hand, Al-Alawi believes that "metonymy and representation... are two types of metaphor, and the most general in them" (Al-Alawi: 2/6), that is: there is a specific relationship to the general between metaphor, metonymy and representation, so metaphor is the most general, and it is followed in particular by each of Metonymy and representation, so he made the metonymy and the representation section in that they are two types of metaphor, and Al-Alawi supports this view with the majority of rhetoric who said the metaphor of the metonymy, while it is reported from Ibn Al-Khatib Al-Razi that he "denied that it is a metaphor, and claimed that the metonymy is to mention a word and give its meaning a second meaning is What is meant is" (Al-Alawi: 1/190), and it was also transmitted in another place that they "attract each other in real and metaphorical ways, and they are both indicative at launch" (Al-Alawi: 1/192).

It seems that its indication of the metaphor and the truth he has is only a signification, and as for its truth, he stands in it with the agreement of the rhetoricians in being a metaphor, because he declares what he chooses in the end, therefore "metaphor, representation, and metonymy are all counted from the valleys of metaphor other than the analogy" (Al Alawi: 3/4).

It must be pointed out that the early rhetoricians did not see metonymy as an advantage that preferred it over truth or disclosure, and that the good in each of them is related to context, meaning, need, and position. (Al-Jahiz: 1/115).

So, the reliance is on the meaning, the method of its delivery, the general attitude accompanying the speech, and the requirement of the speaker and the listener, in accordance with the principle of rhetoric in matching the case. He places the metonymy within the Badi', but rather makes it among the chapters of endless improvements, and the improvement is not essential or important, as is the case in the five sections of Badi' that he mentioned in his book (Ibn al-Mu'taz: 64).

As for the rhetoricians after Abd al-Qaher al-Jurjani, they became more interested in metonymy as an art of metaphor that began, or with interest in it after the fourth century AH. The metonymy is real; Because it is about mentioning a word and conveying its meaning. A second meaning is the intended meaning (Al Alawi: 1/190). Al-Zarkashi quoted Sheikh Izz al-Din that it is also true; Because you used the term in what it was created for, and you wanted it to denote something else, and you did not take it out of being used in what it was created for (Izz ad-Din: 2/301).

Al-Suyuti stated that it is true (Al-Suyuti: 201), and this was also transmitted from Ibn Abd al-Salam, because in his view it was used in what it was written for and I intend with it to denote something else. (Al-Suyuti: 201).

There is an average opinion that the author of the summary said that the metaphor is neither true nor metaphorical, because it is forbidden in the metaphor to mean the real meaning with the metaphor, and it is permissible to do so in the metonymy (Al-Suyuti: 201).

As for those who say metaphorical metaphors are the most among the scholars of rhetoric, Al-Jurjani stated in many places its metaphor (Al-Jarjani: 262-263), and Ibn Al-Atheer made it part of the metaphor (Ibn Al-Atheer: 2/216), and Al-Alawi declared in a place that it weighed between truth and metaphor, saying: The metaphor is attracted by two principles, real and metaphor, and it is indicative of them at all.” (Al-Alawi: 1/192), and it seems that he is talking here by saying about how it works. / 4), and al-Subki, according to his conditional opinion, considers a metaphor as a metaphor in the event that the meaning is not intended, but rather expresses the necessary by the obligatory, and that is that you use the word in a way other than what was set for it (Al-Suyuti: 201).

As for Al-Sakaki, he sees the focus of the science of eloquence on the exposure to the metaphor and the metonymy, so the metaphor moves from the imperative to the imperative, and the metonymy moves from the necessary to the imperative, and in him the metonymy must be delayed because it comes down from the metaphor as the compound from the singular (Al-Sakaki: 118).

The metaphor is realized in the singular words as in our saying (I saw a lion), and as for the metonymy, it is a compound of a group of words, just as the metonymy is a compound of fact and metaphor, while the metaphor can only bear its metaphor, meaning that in the metonymy we understand the original meaning and keep it, but we do not want it, but we want From it a second meaning in which we are more interested, and as for the metaphor, we can only carry the word on the metaphor, and we cannot understand from our saying (I saw a lion) that it is possible that we have seen a lion in the truth.

As for Ibn al-Nazim, he understands from his words that there is a difference between metaphor and metaphor on the one hand, and truth and statement on the other, saying: “The metaphor is more eloquent than the truth and the metaphor is more effective in the soul than the statement. A thing’s claim with evidence and its claim without it” (Ibn Al-Nazim: 156), so we notice that he combines metaphor and metonymy on the one hand and reality and statement on the other, but he did not distinguish between metaphor and metonymy.

And if we paid attention to al-Sakaki’s comment, we would find it approaching Ibn al-Nazim’s saying, for he says: “The word is used either in its meaning alone, which is the truth, or in other than its meaning alone, which is metaphor, and it lacks a predicate preventing it from wanting its meaning, or in its meaning, or in Its meaning and not its meaning together, and it is a metonymy, and it must have a conditional indication, and the truth in the singular and the metonymy both share in being two realities, and they differ in declaring and not declaring, as he adds that the word if it is attributed, its chain is either according to your mind and your knowledge and it is the truth in the sentence, or it is not It is the metaphor in the sentence, then the truth in the sentence is either accompanied by a prescriptive statement, which is the metonymy, or it is not, which is the statement (Al-Sakaki: 414-415).

These two origins determine the relationship of the metonymy to the metaphor in general, which are usage and attribution.

Al-Sakaki made the metonymy and the metaphor two originals, in the metonymy it moves from the necessary to the obligatory, and in the metaphor and metaphor, the transition from the obligatory to the imperative, and the way of moving from the obligatory to the imperative in the metaphor is knowledge, the imperative is equal to the obligatory or less than it. This side comes down from the metaphor as the compound from the singular (Al-Sakaki: 331).

Al-Qurtaji went to what Ibn Al-Atheer went with from imagination and imaging, and he spoke about the relationship of metaphor to moving the soul and the issue of its love for strangeness, he said: “And souls have a strong movement for strange imitations, because if the soul imagines it in something that is not familiar with something admired in the like of it, it finds From the astonishment of what she had imagined that she did not know about something, what he finds that seeks to see what he did not see before the occurrence of what he did not know in himself... And the arts of strangeness and wonderment in mimicry are many, and some of them are stronger than others, and they are more powerful over souls and we have mastered the hearts” (Al-Qarthani) : 1/30).

Al-Razi was not metaphorical, and denied that it is metaphorical (Al-Razi: 103).

Al-Razi agreed in that, Izz al-Din bin Abd al-Salam, and said: "It appears that the metonymy is not a metaphor, because you used the term in what it was placed for, and you wanted it to denote something else, and you did not exclude it from being used in what it was placed for." (Izz al-Din bin Abd al-Salam: 83) .

And from the other group who said that it is a metaphor, Al-Alawi, who said: "Thus the name of the metaphor is comprehensive for its types of metaphor, metonymy and representation" (Al Alawi: 1/197).

Al-Sakaki says in (Miftah Al-Ulum): "It comes down from the metaphor as the compound from the singular" (Al-Sakaki: 157), as for Ibn Al-Atheer, he considered the metaphor as a metaphor, and said: "Every metaphor is a metaphor, and not every metaphor is a metaphor" (Ibn Al-Atheer: 2/197), and Al-Qazwini went in his book (The Clarification and Al-Talkhiz) that the metonymy is a mediator between truth and metaphor (Al-Qazwini: 308).

Al-Desouki justified this by saying: The metaphor is taken out on the basis that it is a mediation, neither a truth nor a metaphor, but it is not a truth; Because it is the word used in what it was created for, and the metonymy is not that, and as for that it is not a metaphor; Because he stipulated in it the presumption that prevents the will of the truth, and the metonymy is not, and that is why he took it out of the definition of metaphor (Al-Desouki: 2/176).

As for Al-Suyuti, he summarized the different schools of thought in the metonymy and limited it to four: "The first of which is the truth, Ibn Salam said: It is apparent because it was used in what it was written for, and I mean by it indications for others.

The second is that it is a metaphor, and the third is that it is neither a reality nor a metaphor, and to it Al-Qazwini went in the summary to prevent him in the metaphor that the real meaning is intended with the metaphor and it is permissible in it.

As for the fourth, which is the choice of Sheikh Taqi al-Din al-Subki, it is divided into a fact and a metaphor. That the word is used in what it was created for it to benefit other than what it was created for it, and the metaphor of it is that it intends to use it other than its intended use and benefit" (Al-Suyuti: 1/111-112).

It seems that their disagreement in the metaphor is real or metaphor?, similar to their disagreement about the simile, for those who considered it real, but saw that the word in it is used in its meaning, you in your saying: Zaid wide-breasted, a metaphor for dream, and a lot of ashes, a metaphor for generosity, you find the words in Each of these sentences has been used in its true meaning for those who see it as such, but the metaphor in them symbolizes it, which is the adjective.

The metonymy in this is similar to the simile; For in our saying: Zaid is like a lion, the two words each have their meaning, but the metaphor is for those who consider the simile a metaphor, and if it does not symbolize anything, it is true, as it may be broad-breasted in reality, and it may be a lot of ashes because it is cooked for others for a fee, so the metaphor is no longer available. This is what Ibn al-Atheer intended when he said: It is every word that denotes a meaning that can be carried on both sides of the truth and metaphor, and this is the opinion of the Alawi and what he went to as well.

Based on this, the metonymy is metaphorical if the word denotes an adjective or a description, since it is not intended by its true significance.

From this view a dispute arose between the scholars of rhetoric and its scholars, and on this, whoever considers the simile to be true sees the metonymy as well, and among these (Al-Razi), and whoever goes to the simile is a metaphor makes the metaphor also, and from these Al-Sakaki, and those who are attributed to the truth or metaphor, he is a patron What the word indicates.

The metaphor is on the surface real, although what it indicates makes it a metaphor.

Al-Zamakhshari considered the metaphor as a kind of metaphor, as he presented its examples in the context of the metaphors he mentions without stating that it is a metaphor (Al-Zamakhshari: 54), and he explained the metaphorical connotations in an explanation that makes it clear that it is a metaphor.

Al-Suyuti stated that Al-Zamakhshari devised a kind of metonymy, which is "to deliberately refer to a sentence whose meaning is contrary to the apparent meaning, and to take the summary without considering its vocabulary in terms of truth and metaphor, and expresses the intention" (Al-Suyuti: 29).

We must know what the rhetoricians called most of them, and made them agree on the metaphor of the metaphor. Al-Jurjani sees: "In the metaphor and the metonymy, the claim of the thing is clear, and it is the mention of what is inseparable from it other than the truth and the statement, and a difference between the claim of the thing with it and his claim without it" (Al-Jurjani: 156), and this justification that he conveys to us after his transfer to the consensus on the preference of metaphor and metaphor over truth, and the evidence that he intends is the presumption that is brought to confirm the metaphor and the metonymy, and to remove the suspicion of the truth (Al-Jurjani: 407), which means that the relationship and the circumstance calls for the use of the metaphor, or allow it to be used.

And when he talked about the meaning and the meaning of the meaning, he stated that the truth leads us towards the meaning, and that metaphor leads us towards a first meaning, and this meaning leads us to the meaning of the meaning (Al-Jurjani: 262), and Al-Jurjani sees that this long road and the inference of the Emirate of the first meaning towards the second meaning gives the text more beauty than If the listener arrives at the meaning

directly, and thus bypasses the problem related to the difference between metaphor and metonymy on the one hand, and disclosure on the other hand, by placing the basis of the meaning of the meaning, and metonymy leads us to the meaning of the meaning as well, which justifies saying its metaphor.

As for Ibn al-Atheer, he cited similar words to al-Jurjani's, and he sees that the advantage in our saying: I saw a lion: "You demonstrated to the borrower the excess courage and the abundant strength from a face that was more eloquent and affirmed, and you made it imperative for him positively that he is stronger and stronger, because you proved it with evidence and evidence" (Ibn al-Atheer: 2). / 82), the transfer of the word from one meaning to another is done for the sake of emphasis and exaggeration, and the metaphor of the word lies in establishing a witness to it.

In another place, metaphor or what he calls transference is made on sharing between what is transmitted from him and what is transmitted to him, and transfer is not on participation, then he singled out the second type of them with the benefit of expanding speech (Ibn al-Atheer: 2/71).

Ibn al-Atheer searched for a benefit related to the recipient, which is imagining, when he said: "Know that metaphor is more appropriate to use than reality... because it has been proven and verified that the benefit of rhetorical speech is to prove the intended purpose in the same listener by imagining and making images until he can almost look at it with his eyes." (Ibn al-Atheer: 1/ 82).

Second: The analogy between metaphor and non-fiction.

The rhetoricians defined the simile and most of their definitions lead to one meaning, which is: The simile connects two or more things in one or more attributes, and the difference of the people of rhetoric in this art in this attribute or attributes, and the amount of agreement and the difference between them.

Qudamah said in his definition of the simile: "The best simile is what occurred between the two things, their sharing of attributes is more than their isolation in them until it brings them to a state of union (Qudamah bin Jaafar: 82).

Al-Rumani went on to say that the simile: "It is the contract that one of the two things blocks the other in goodness or reason" (Al-Rumani: 74).

Al-Askari said about him: "It is the description that one of the descriptors deputizes the other with a tool" (Al-Askari: 293).

As for Ibn Rashiq, he said: "Tashbeeh is an attribute of a thing with what is close to it and is similar to it from one side or directions, not from all its sides, because if it fits it completely, it would be it" (Al-Qayrawani: 1/286).

Al-Sakaki went on to say that he calls two parties, suspicious and suspicious of him, and a commonality between them and from one aspect, and a difference from another (Al-Sakaki: 157).

Ibn al-Atheer said: The analogy is to prove to the suspect a ruling from the rulings of the suspect (Ibn al-Atheer: 1/388).

Al-Qazwini said: It indicates the sharing of one thing with another in the meaning of (Al-Qazwini: 213).

Al-Zarkashi said: It is an indication that two things share a description that is one of the attributes of the same thing, such as perfume in musk, luminosity in the sun, and light in the moon (Al-Zarkashi: 3/414).

Al-Sijlmasi said: It is the imaginary saying that something is in something (Al-Sijlmasi: 50).

*** As for the analogy between being permitted or not:**

The scholars of rhetoric differed about whether the simile is metaphorical or not. Some of them said that it is not metaphor, and one of the first scholars who declared this was Abd al-Qaher al-Jarjani, he said: "Every person who uses an explicit analogy does not have the transfer of the word from his concern nor necessitate its purpose, so if you say: (Zayd is like a lion), and (this news is like the sun in fame), and (has an opinion like a sword in the light), it was not possible to transfer the utterance from its subject, and if the matter was otherwise, it would have been necessary that there should be no analogy in this world except that it is metaphor and this is impossible, because the analogy A meaning from the meanings, and it has letters and names denoting it, so if it is stated clearly by mentioning what is intended to denote it, it is like speech in reality, like ruling in all other meanings, so know it" (Al-Jurjani: 221).

Al-Jurjani followed al-Razi, al-Matrazi, al-Sakaki, Ibn al-Zamalkani, al-Halabi, al-Qazwini, and the commentators on al-Tulkhis.

Ibn al-Qayyim al-Jawziyya referred to this by saying: "The investigators, among the later scholars of this industry and its experts, have concluded that the simile is not a metaphor, because it is one of the meanings and not letters and words that indicate it" (Ibn al-Qayyim: 54).

Al-Zarkashi said: "And the investigators believe that it is a fact. Al-Zanjani said in the standard: the simile is not a metaphor because it is one of the meanings, and it has words that indicate it by position, so there is no transfer of the word from its subject, but it is a prelude to the one who took the path of metaphor and representation, because it is like the original to them, and it is like a branch His, and what falls from it in the space of metaphor for the literalists is the one who comes to the limit of metaphor, and Sheikh Izz El-Din mediated and said: If it is

with a letter, then it is true, or by deleting it, it is a metaphor, based on the fact that the deletion is from the door of metaphor” (Izz El-Din: 3/415) .

Others of the scholars went to the fact that it is a metaphor, and Ibn al-Qayyim al-Jawziyya referred to this by saying: “And what the majority of the people of industry agree upon is that the simile is a kind of metaphor, and all of their classifications state that and refer to it (Ibn al-Qayyim: 54).

The most famous one who stated that the analogy is from the metaphor is Ibn Rashiq, he said: “As for the metaphor being included in the analogy, it is because the similarities in most things are similar in comparison to forgiveness and convention, not the truth” (Al-Qayrawani: 2/268).

As for Ibn al-Atheer, he divided the metaphor into two parts: the expansion of speech, and the simile, and the simile is of two kinds: the complete simile, and the omitted simile (metaphor), then he said: “If you wish, I say: The metaphor is divided into: an expansion of speech, an analogy, and a metaphor, and it does not come out.” About one of these three divisions, so wherever it was found, it was metaphorical” (Ibn Al-Atheer: 1/356-366), and he said: “Do you not see that if the simile is found alone, that is metaphorical” (Al-Alawi: 1/197).

Al-Alawi said that it is a metaphor, and he said: “This is the name of the metaphor, as it includes the types of metaphor, metonymy, and representation” (Al-Alawi: 1/196).

Al-Alawi spoke about the analogy, saying: “The chosen one for us is that it is numbered in the sciences of rhetoric, because of its accuracy and gentleness, and because the word is acquired with elegance and grace; He is close to a relative after being one of the most eloquent rules of rhetoric, and there is no great benefit related to him” (Al-Alawi: 1/197). As for Al-Zamakhshari, he introduced the simile under the heading (and metaphor) in the basis of rhetoric, and he cited examples of simile in the context of the metaphors he presents (Al-Jarjani) : 43).

The analogy is not based on justification, so the analogy is real, and so is the suspect, but the issue takes another face when we return to the rhetorical scholars and other linguists deny their view of the analogy in terms of its significance to the truth or metaphor, and this view introduces us to the way of understanding the significance of the linguistic structure, and the enforcement Beyond the linguistic formula on which it is based, it is a way of inspiring what may be behind this formula of justice that adds to it spectra of meaning, and this is what we find among the tasters of analogy who looked at its linguistic form as a special formula, whose manufacture is due to imagination more than reality .

In this regard, Al-Ramani Al-Nahwi distinguished between two types of analogy, the first: the analogy of two things that agree in themselves, such as the analogy of the Nile water as the water of the Euphrates, and the essence with the substance, and the second: the analogy of two different things with oneself, united by a common meaning between them, as you say: Hatim is like a cloud, for the analogy is between two things that agree A real analogy, and the second different analogy is a metaphor for exaggeration (Al-Rumani: 118).

Al-Ramani’s speech in this regard is the reference of Abd al-Qahir al-Jarjani in his study of the analogy in the secrets of rhetoric. He also spoke about two types of simile, the first: it does not need to be interpreted, and the other is the resemblance obtained by a multiplication of interpretation. , and the second: as you say: an argument like the sun in its appearance (Al-Jurjani: 70-73).

And if Al-Jurjani did not take into account the metaphor of the simile, and he did not take the words of Al-Ramani in this regard, then his talk about interpretation does not stray far from the words of Al-Ramani, so the analogy in this case is a kind of search for (the meaning of meaning), which is the course of Al-Jurjani’s work in the metaphor.

Through the foregoing, because the analogy is metaphorical or not, it seems that we cannot pass a general judgment on this art in terms of being a fact or a metaphor, since the analogy is types according to the completeness and incompleteness of its pillars. When we say: “Zayd is like a lion in courage,” every word here denotes its true meaning.

Al-Jurjani, in his lack of metaphor for simile, clarified this with complete examples.

As for Zaid as a lion, and Zaid as a lion, they both fall into the metaphor in a way. In our saying: Zaid is like a lion, the intent is not merely to compare Zaid to a lion, but rather the intent of this formulation indicates his courage; This is due to the custom that made the lion a symbol of courage, a time here when “Zayd is like a lion” was not real, but rather a metaphor for those who see that; Because Zayd does not resemble the lion in anything, as we have restricted what the apparent pronunciation indicates, and thus both groups are right in what he said; Because both of them looked at the analogy from one side, and perhaps this is what Al-Jurjani intended in his saying: “If the matter was different for you, it would be necessary for there to be no analogy in this world except that it is a metaphor” (Al-Jarjani: 221).

We conclude from this that not every simile is a metaphor, and not every simile is real.

The later people differentiated the analogy with its linguistic meaning and the analogy with its idiomatic meaning, so they considered the analogy with its linguistic meaning to be real, and the analogy with its idiomatic meaning is a metaphor (Al-Subki: 292).

Dr. Ahmed Matlab went on to talk about the metaphor of simile or not, saying: “The truth is that simile is a metaphor, because it depends on the connection between two things or things that cannot be explained by the

truth, and if interpreted as such, it would have become a lie, and it is the art of much use in the speech of the Arabs. And it seems that not moving in it from one meaning to another, as in the metaphor, called them to take it out of the metaphor, which is the use of the word for something other than what it was placed for, or the attribution of an order to another for the sake of expansion” (Ahmad Matlab: 2/173).

They also differed in the location of the analogy from the science of eloquence, for Al-Sakaki, Al-Qazwini, and the commentators did not consider it to be from the science of eloquence. In simile, and therefore it is an independent art in the science of rhetoric intentionally, even if some of its chapters depend on it; Because some chapters depend on others, it does not necessitate that what is based on is a prelude to art (Al-Desouki: 2/283).

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